

Synthesis and characterization of heteroleptic iridium(III) complexes incorporating 5-arylaazo-8-hydroxyquinoline as coligands : DFT/TDDFT studies on the electronic structures and spectral properties

Amit Maity and Kajal Krishna Rajak*

Inorganic Chemistry Section, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : kajalrajak@rediffmail.com, kkrajak@chemistry.jdvu.ac.in, maity.amit345@gmail.com

Manuscript received 30 August 2017, revised 16 September 2017, accepted 18 September 2017

Abstract : The orange coloured complexes of general formula $[\text{Ir}(\text{2-pypy})_2(\text{hq})]$ have been prepared in exceptional yield by reaction of $[\text{Ir}(\text{2-pypy})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ with Hhq under argon atmosphere in 1 : 1 mixture of ethanol and dichloromethane in alkaline condition. Here hq^- is deprotonated form of 5-phenylazo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Hhq^1), 5-(2-naphthylazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline (Hhq^2) and 5-(2-fluorineazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline (Hhq^3). The elemental analysis, ESI mass spectroscopic measurements, IR spectroscopy and ^1H NMR spectroscopy guarantee the formation of desired complexes. The ground and excited-state geometries, absorption, and phosphorescence properties of three Ir^{III} complexes were investigated by DFT and TDDFT methods. The natural transition orbital (NTO) and spin density analysis reveals the nature of excitations. The lowest lying triplet excited is connected with the ^3IL and ^3ML excited state is consistent with the emission like transition.

Keywords : Iridium(III) complexes, spectral study, DFT and TDDFT study, $^3\text{ILCT}$ - $^3\text{MLCT}$ excited state.

Introduction

The study of transition metal complexes exhibiting highly efficient room-temperature phosphorescence properties are of abiding interest¹⁻¹³. Especially the Ir^{III} complexes are to be considered as a promising member due to their unique combination of chemical stability, strong visible absorption, excited state reactivity, photoredox chemistry and catalytic properties¹⁴⁻²⁵. These properties of such complexes can be attributed to the strong spin-orbit coupling provided by the Ir^{III} ion as well as strong metal ligand interaction as a consequence the triplet metal to ligand charge transfer excited state ($^3\text{MLCT}$) can emit molecular phosphorescence by borrowing the intensity of the $^1\text{MLCT}$ excited state. The discovery²⁶ of an OLED bearing cyclometalated iridium(III) complex $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{Cl}_2]_2$ (2-pypy = 2-phenylpyridine) as a dopant has been accelerated the interest in the chemistry of the heteroleptic iridium(III) complexes bearing coordinated phenylpyridine moiety. The property of such

compounds can be tuned through judicious molecular engineering by control of ligands^{14,17,21-23}. This has prompted us to design and synthesis of heteroleptic Ir^{III} complexes with substituted 8-hydroxyquinolate moiety as the studies of iridium(III) complexes having $[\text{Ir}(\text{2-pypy})_2]^+$ moiety with bidentate 8-oxyquinolate ligands are rare²⁷⁻³¹.

It is cited in the literature that iridium(III) 8-oxyquinolate complexes display an intense electronic transition in the visible region (360–390 nm) due to $\text{Ir}^{\text{III}} (t_{2g}) \rightarrow \text{hq}(\pi^*)$ singlet metal-to-ligand charge-transfer ($^1\text{MLCT}$) excitations with an extinction coefficient, ϵ , span in the range = (18000–35000) $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ for all complexes. The fine tuning of HOMO and LUMO energy levels as well as the band gap of such complexes are achievable by introducing the π -conjugations into the ancillary ligand. In connection to this, the inclusion of a photoresponsive π -conjugations component into a supramolecular structure is a promising synthetic approach to isolate the photo as-

sisted isomeric species that may be quite valuable as model systems for theoretical studies and can be applied in photo switches or molecular memory units. It is believed that the isomerism is associated with the transfer of energy from the metal-to-ligand charge-transfer excited state, $^3\text{MLCT}$, to a ligand centered state, $^3\text{IL}_{\text{trans-L}}$ of the ligand.

With the above state of development have prompted us to design and synthesize iridium(III) 8-oxyquinolate complexes with three different ancillary ligands containing extended π -conjugation in order to improve the light-harvesting capabilities in respect to both the molar extinction coefficient and the bathochromic shift of the absorption. Herein we introduced an azoaryl moiety at the 5-position to Hhq ligand in order to achieve the bathochromic shift of the MLCT absorption peaks in the visible region with enhancement of molar extinction coefficients compared to that of 8-hydroxyquinol having no extended π -conjugation. The complexes are characterized by IR, UV-Vis, NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) spectroscopic techniques. The photophysical properties of the complexes were also investigated.

Experimental

Materials :

Literature³² procedure was applied to prepare $[\text{Ir}_2(\text{ppy})_4\text{Cl}_2]$. All the chemicals and solvents were pure and used without extra refinement.

Physical measurements :

UV-Vis spectra were done on a Perkin-Elmer LAMBDA 25 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were observed with a Perkin-Elmer L-0100 spectrophotometer. Bruker FT 300 MHz and 400 MHz spectrometer were used to determine ^1H NMR spectra. The atom-numbering scheme used for ^1H NMR same as that used in the crystallography. Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) spectra were investigated on a Micromass Qtof YA 263 mass spectrometer. Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were done on Perkin-Elmer 2400 series II analyzer. The emission data were taken on a Horiba FluroMax-4 fluorescence spectrometer. For all luminescence measurements slit width of 2 nm was used for both excitation and emission. Quantum yields of the complexes were

determined in freeze-pump-thaw-degassed solutions of the complexes by a relative method using quinine sulfate in the same solvent as the standard [$\Phi_{\text{std}} = 0.54$ (at 298 K) in 0.1 M H_2SO_4 at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 350 \text{ nm}$]³³ by usual method. The fluorescence life time was obtained by usual method³⁴. The quantum yields were calculated using eq. (1),³⁵.

$$\Phi_{\text{r}} = \Phi_{\text{std}} \frac{A_{\text{std}}}{A_{\text{r}}} \frac{I_{\text{r}}}{I_{\text{std}}} \frac{\eta_{\text{r}}^2}{\eta_{\text{std}}^2} \quad (1)$$

where, Φ_{r} and Φ_{std} are the quantum yields of unknown and standard samples, A_{r} and A_{std} (< 0.1) are the solution absorbances at the excitation wavelength (λ_{ex}), I_{r} and I_{std} are the integrated emission intensities, and η_{r} and η_{std} are the refractive indices of the solvent. Experimental errors in the reported luminescence quantum yields were about 10%. Time-correlated single-photon-counting (TCSPC) measurements were carried out for the luminescence decay of complexes in dichloromethane. For TCSPC measurement, the photoexcitation was made at 450 nm using a picosecond diode laser (IBH Nanoled-07) in an IBH Fluorocube apparatus. Hamamatsu MCP photomultiplier (R3809) was used to collect the fluorescence decay data and were analyzed by using IBH DAS6 software.

Computational details :

The geometrical structures of the singlet ground state (S_0) and the lowest lying triplet excited state (T_1) were optimized by the DFT³⁶ method with B3LYP exchange correlation functional⁴² approach. The geometry of the complexes was fully optimized in solution phase without any symmetry constraints. There is a good agreement between the theoretical and experimental structures. On the basis of the optimized ground and excited state geometry structures, the absorption and emission spectra properties in dichloromethane (CH_2Cl_2) media were calculated by time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT)³⁷ approach associated with the conductor-like polarisable continuum model (CPCM)³⁸. We computed the lowest 50 singlet-singlet transition and results of the TD calculations were qualitatively very similar. The TDDFT approach had been demonstrated to be reli-

able for calculating spectra properties of many transition metal complexes³⁹. Due to the presence of electronic correlation in the TDDFT (B3LYP) method it can yield more accurate electronic excitation energies. Hence TDDFT had been shown to provide a reasonable spectral feature for our complex of investigation. A relativistic effective core potential (ECP)⁴⁰ on Ir replaced the inner core electrons leaving the outer core [(5s)²(5p)⁶] electrons and the (5d⁶) valence electrons of Ir^{III}. In the calculation a “double- ξ ” quality basis set LANL2DZ was adopted as the basis set for Ir atoms. For H atom we used 6-31G basis set and for C, N and O atoms 6-31+G basis set was used for the optimization of both the ground state and the lowest lying triplet excited state geometries of all complexes.

Finally to understand the nature of excited states involved in absorption and emission processes natural transition orbital (NTO) analysis has been performed for all complexes. This approach provides the most compact representation of the electronic transitions on terms of an expansion into single particle orbitals by diagonalizing the transition density matrix associated with each excitation. Figures showing MOs, NTOs and the difference density plots were prepared by using the GaussView 5.1 software. All the calculations were performed with the Gaussian 09 software package⁴¹. Gausssum 2.1 program⁴² was used to calculate the molecular orbital contributions from groups or atoms.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The three substituted 8-hydroxyquinoline Hhq¹-Hhq³ [Chart 1] (general abbreviation Hhq) were synthesized according to the literature procedure⁴³ and were used as a monoanionic N, O donor ligand for the preparation of the Ir^{III} complexes (Scheme 1). In order to tune the photophysical properties of the complexes an azoaryl group at the 5-position was introduced on to the 8-hydroxyquinoline moiety. It is to be noted that the choice of such ligands helps us to achieve our goal in the context of synthesis of mononuclear iridium(III) complexes (Scheme 1) with interesting optical properties.

Chart 1

The stoichiometric reaction of [Ir(2-pypy)₂Cl]₂ (where 2-pypy is 2-phenyl pyridine) with appropriate Hhq in boiling toluene under argon atmosphere afforded orange coloured complexes of general formula [Ir(2-pypy)₂hq] in good yield (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Schematic representation for the synthesis of the complexes.

The elemental analysis and ¹H NMR, IR and ESI-mass spectroscopic measurements confirm the formation of the synthesized complex (see Results and discussion portion).

The complexes were prepared by the same general methods (Scheme 1). The elemental analysis and ESI-mass spectroscopic measurements confirm the formation of the synthesized complexes. Details are given here for a representative case.

[Ir(2-pyppy)₂(hq¹)], **1** : A mixture of Hhq¹ (50 mg, 0.20 mmol) and [(2-pyppy)₂Ir(μ-Cl)]₂ (150 mg, 0.20 mmol) in a 1 : 1 mixture of dichloromethane and ethanol (40 mL) and 2–3 drops of triethylamine was refluxed for 24 h under argon atmosphere. After cooling to room temperature, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was dissolved in a minimum volume of benzene and subjected to a column chromatography on a silica gel column (60–120 mesh). An orange band was eluted using 30% acetonitrile in benzene solution. An orange coloured solid was obtained after removal of solvent under reduced pressure. The product on diffusion from dichloromethane-hexane afforded non diffracting orange coloured crystals. Yield : 130 mg (65%). Elemental Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₂₆N₅OIr : C, 59.34; H, 3.50; N, 9.35. Found : C, 59.43; H, 3.57; N, 9.39; ESI-MS (CH₂Cl₂) : *m/z* 750.25 [M+H]⁺; IR_{exptl} (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 2354, 1459, 1408, 1323, 1239; ν(N=N) 1576; ¹H NMR_{exptl} {300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm), *J* (Hz)} : 6.5 (C25-*H*, s), 6.34 (C24-*H*, d, *J*=7.4), 8.7 (C11-*H*, d, *J*=4.9), 7.77 (C10-*H*, s), 8.23 (C29-*H*, d, *J*=9), 8.70 (C22-*H*, d, *J*=4.9), 9.28 (C2-*H*, d, *J*=7.4), 6.8–7.6 (23H, ArH).

[Ir(2-pyppy)₂(hq²)], **2** : Yield : 132 mg (63%). Elemental Anal. Calcd. for C₄₁H₂₈N₅OIr : C, 61.64; H, 3.53; N, 8.77. Found : C, 61.79; H, 3.59; N, 8.78; ESI-MS (CH₂Cl₂) : *m/z* 800.28 [M+H]⁺; IR_{exptl} (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 2370, 1459, 1244, 1307, 1173; ν(N=N) 1570; ¹H NMR_{exptl} {300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm), *J* (Hz)} : 6.5 (C25-*H*, d, *J*=7.4), 6.4 (C24-*H*, d, *J*=6.96), 8.9 (C11-*H*, d, *J*=8.1), 7.79 (C10-*H*, s), 8.41 (C29-*H*, d, *J*=8.9), 8.71 (C22-*H*, d, *J*=5.3), 9.38 (C2-*H*, d, *J*=7.93), 6.8–7.8 (27H, ArH).

[Ir(2-pyppy)₂(hq³)], **3** : Yield : 140 mg (70%). Elemental Anal. Calcd. for C₄₄H₃₀N₅OIr : C, 63.14; H, 3.61; N, 8.37. Found : C, 63.28; H, 3.68; N, 8.43; ESI-MS (CH₂Cl₂) : *m/z* 838.26 [M+Na]⁺; IR_{exptl} (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 2375, 1458, 1328, 1253, 1152; ν(N=N) 1568; ¹H NMR_{exptl} {400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ (ppm), *J* (Hz)} : 6.7 (C25-*H*, d, *J*=7.2), 6.4 (C24-*H*, d, *J*=7.6), 8.7 (C11-*H*, d, *J*=5.2), 8.2 (C29-*H*, d, *J*=8.8), 7.7 (C12-*H*, d, *J*=4), 9.3 (C2-*H*, s), 6.8–

7.6 (30H, ArH).

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the complexes were recorded in a KBr disk. The calculated IR spectra of all the complexes were reported. The characteristic IR data were given in the Experimental section. The characteristic N=N stretches were observed ~1570 cm⁻¹ in all three complexes. IR spectrum of complex **1** is given in electronic supporting information (Fig. 16).

NMR spectra :

The complexes are diamagnetic and display well resolved ¹H in CDCl₃. Signals were assigned on the basis of intensity, spin-spin coupling patterns and chemical shift values. The numbering schemes were based on the Chart 1 and Scheme 1 and see optimisation structure with numbering of each atom in Fig. 1. For complex **1** and for complex **2** and **3** see supporting information Fig. 17 and Fig. 18 respectively.

In all the complexes C24-*H* and C25-*H* are observed as doublet ~6.4–~6.7 ppm. C11-*H* as well as C22-*H* is observed as a doublet in the range 8.7–8.9 ppm. C29-*H* in all the complexes is observed near ~8.2–8.4 ppm as a doublet. All the aromatic protons span in the range 6.8–7.8 ppm. All the ¹H NMR spectra given in electronic supporting information (Fig. 10, Fig. 11, Fig. 12).

Mass spectra :

All the ESI-mass spectra of all the complexes are given in electronic supporting information (Fig. 13, Fig. 14, Fig. 15) and all data are given in Experimental section.

Geometry optimization, electronic structure, charge distribution analysis :

The diamagnetic nature of the complexes at room temperature representing their singlet ground state t_{2g}⁶. The geometry optimization for all the complexes were performed in solution phases in their both ground singlet (S₀) and lowest lying excited triplet (T₁) spin state. The optimized structures of the complex **1** at singlet ground state are shown in Fig. 1 while the same for complex **2** and **3** are given in electronic supporting information (Fig. 17 and Fig. 18 respectively). The geometries possess a distorted octahedral

Fig. 1. Optimisation structure of complex **1** in ground state.

Table 1. Comparison of the selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for Complex **1** in both singlet ground state and triplet excited state

Bond lengths				Bond angles and dihedral angle (D)			
Singlet state (S_0)		Triplet state (T_1)		Singlet state (S_0)		Triplet state (T_1)	
Ir1-N3	2.185	Ir1-N3	2.185	N1-Ir1-O1	88.483	N1-Ir1-O1	88.723
Ir1-N1	2.063	Ir1-N1	2.059	C1-Ir1-C12	90.808	C1-Ir1-C12	90.796
Ir1-O1	2.212	Ir1-O1	2.213	C1-Ir1-N2	96.998	C1-Ir1-N2	97.713
Ir1-N2	2.071	Ir1-N2	2.073	C1-Ir1-N3	172.693	C1-Ir1-N3	172.753
Ir1-C1	2.014	Ir1-C1	2.014	N1-Ir1-N2	175.361	N1-Ir1-N2	175.810
Ir1-C12	2.027	Ir1-C12	2.025	N2-Ir1-N3	88.543	N2-Ir1-N3	87.612
N4-N5	1.291	N4-N5	1.328	C32-N5-N4-C33		C32-N5-N4-C33	
N5-C33	1.424	N5-C33	1.386	D = 179.761		D = -110.177	
N4-C32	1.291	N4-C32	1.344				

arrangement around the Ir^{III} centre. In all complexes the calculated Ir-C1, Ir-N3, Ir-N1 and Ir-O1 bond distances occur near 2.01, 2.18, 2.06 and 2.21 Å respectively which are in very good agreement with the experimental values reported in the literature^{10,12} and the slight discrepancy may be due to the crystal lattice distortion existing in real molecules. Table 1 compare the optimized geometrical parameters of compound **1** in both singlet and triplet state iridium. The geometrical parameters for both ground and triplet state for other two complexes are given in supporting information [Table 6(a) and Table 6(b)]. Bond angles are reproduced to the same degree of accuracy

as bond lengths. The optimized geometries of all the complexes in both S_0 and T_1 states do not show significant differences in the coordination sphere around the iridium centre corroborates with the similar fashion of binding of the ligands in the complexes.

For all complexes in the ground S_0 state, the ligand moiety (hq) is planar and the quinoline moiety remains *trans* to the aromatic moiety attached to N=N bond which is characterized by the $\angle C33-N5-N4-C32 \approx 179.8^\circ-179.9^\circ$ (for complex **1**, **2**, **3**). The calculated N=N bond distance for all complexes occurs near 1.28. In the triplet excited state (T_1), the geometry around N=N bond is completely different

from the geometry observed in the S_0 state. In T_1 state the quinoline moiety become *cis* to the aromatic moiety attached to $N=N$ bond which is also characterized by the $\angle C33-N5-N4-C32 \approx 109^\circ-111^\circ$ (for **1**, **2**, **3**).

The partial frontier molecular orbital compositions

and energy levels of **1** in singlet ground state (S_0) are given in Table 2 while that for other complexes are given in supporting information (Table 7 and Table 8). Fig. 2 signifies the partial molecular orbital diagram bearing isodensity frontier molecular orbital which are mainly associated with the electronic tran-

Fig. 2. Partial molecular orbital diagram with some isodensity frontier molecular orbital mainly involved in the electronic transitions for complex **1**, **2** and **3**. The arrows indicate the HOMO-LUMO energy gaps.

Table 2. Frontier molecular orbital composition (%) in the ground state for **1**

Orbital	Energy (eV)	Contribution (%)				Main bond type
		Ir	2-pypy	Hhq ¹		
				Hq+azo	Aromatic system	
LUMO+5	-1.23	0	99	1	0	π^* (2-pypy)
LUMO+4	-1.36	1	92	6	0	π^* (2-pypy)
LUMO+3	-1.77	3	90	7	0	π^* (2-pypy)
LUMO+2	-1.83	4	72	23	2	π^* (2-pypy) + π^* (Hhq ¹)
LUMO+1	-1.87	1	31	63	6	π^* (2-pypy) + π^* (Hhq ¹)
LUMO	-2.63	1	0	77	18	π^* (Hhq ¹)
HOMO	-5.4	14	3	71	12	d(Ir) + π (Hhq ¹)
HOMO-1	-5.49	43	51	6	0	d(Ir) + π (2-pypy)
HOMO-2	-6.24	68	25	6	1	d(Ir) + π (2-pypy)
HOMO-3	-6.31	1	0	92	7	π (Hhq ¹)
HOMO-4	-6.32	30	60	7	4	d(Ir) + π (2-pypy) + π (Hhq ¹)
HOMO-5	-6.47	27	61	8	4	d(Ir) + π (2-pypy) + π (Hhq ¹)

sitions for complexes.

In all complexes, the electron density in HOMO (H) mainly reside on quinoline moiety including azo group (66–71%) (10–15) and aromatic system (in the range 12–25%) attached to N=N bond along with some metal d orbital (9–15%). The electron densities of HOMO-1 for **1** and **3** are mainly associated with metal d and 2-pypy moiety while that for **2** electron densities are reside on the ligand part. The HOMO-2 and HOMO-3 orbitals are energetically close to each other and the energy difference being 0.07, 0.06 and 0.06 for **1**, **2** and **3** respectively. In HOMO-2 the electron density of metal d orbitals lying on the range 40–68%. For **1** and **2**, the electron density of HOMO-3 are found at the ligand parts however it is distributed both in metal d orbitals and ligand part in **3**. The HOMO-3 and HOMO-4 are almost degenerate (energy difference ~ 0.01 eV in **1** and **3**, ~ 0.02 eV in **2**). HOMO-4 is composed with the metal d orbitals and ligand electron densities. LUMO (L) and L+1 of all complexes originates from ligand π^* orbital localized on N=N bond, quinoline moiety and aromatic system attached to N=N bond contribution as well as 2-pypy fragment. L+2 orbital shows a strong contribution of the π^* of 2-pypy moiety.

The isodensity surfaces of the Highest and Lowest Singly Occupied Molecular Orbitals, namely HSOMO and LSOMO for all species, at the relaxed T₁ geom-

etry are shown in Fig. 3. Also, the corresponding electrons spin density, which is defined as the difference between α and β spin contributions to the total electron density, are depicted in Fig. 3. The analysis of the singly occupied molecular orbitals at the T₁ geometry showed that the LSOMO is mainly located on the quinoline moiety and resembles the HOMO of the corresponding S₀ geometry. On the other hand π orbital of quinoline moiety and N=N bond contributes primarily to HSOMO along with a small contribution arises from the π orbital of the aromatic system attached to N=N bond and HSOMO resembles the corresponding LUMO and LUMO+1 of the S₀ geometry. The spin density plot at T₁ state for all the complexes illustrates that the spin density is mainly localized on the ligand moiety (hq) along with very minor contribution from metal d orbitals thus the lowest-lying triplet excited state (T₁) is the virtually intraligand (³IL) excited state (ligand-localized) in all complexes.

Absorption spectral properties :

The absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded in dichloromethane at room temperature. Fig. 4 shows the experimental absorption spectra for all mononuclear complexes, respectively. The compounds display three well resolved absorption bands within the range ~ 258 –520 nm. The absorption band in the region 500–520 and 429–440 nm for all compounds

Fig. 3. Isodensity surface plots of the highest and lowest singly occupied molecular orbitals, HSOMO and LSOMO, respectively, along with the corresponding electron spin density, for the complexes **1**, **2** and **3** at their T_1 state geometry. Blue and green colors show regions of positive and negative difference between the alpha and beta electron densities, respectively.

can presumably assigned to an admixture of metal-to-ligand charge-transfer ($^1\text{MLCT}$) transition and spin-allowed $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ $^1\text{ILCT}$ and $^1\text{LLCT}$ transitions while the lowest lying absorption band at 520 nm for complex **3** have purely ligand centered $^1\text{ILCT}$ character. The band ~ 260 nm is mainly $^1\text{MLCT}$ character along with a little $^1\text{ILCT}$ character. These assignments were supported by theoretical calculations [from spin density plot and also from natural transition orbital (NTO) analysis]. The photophysical parameters of complexes are given in Table 4. The calculated absorption energies associated with their oscillator strengths, the main configurations and their assignments as well as the experimental result of complex **1** is given in Table 3 and for **2** and **3** given in supporting information (Table 9 and Table 10).

In order to get better insight into the nature of absorption, we have calculated an NTO analysis based on the calculated transition density matrices. This method offers to be a most promising representation of the transition density between the ground and excited states in terms of an expansion into single-particle transitions (hole and electron states for each given excitation). The unoccupied and occupied NTOs are

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of complexes **1**, **2** and **3** in dichloromethane at room temperature.

defined as “electron” and “hole” transition orbitals, respectively. In addition to this the NTOs are not the same as virtual and occupied MO pairs from the ground state calculations. Fig. 6 describes the natural transition orbitals (NTOs) for complex **1** while the same for other complexes **2** and **3** are given in supporting information (Fig. 19 and Fig. 20). It is clear from the TDDFT NTOs analysis the bands in the region 258–520 nm for all mononuclear complexes can be logi-

Fig. 5. Display the accompanying electron density redistributions in complex **1**, **2** and **3**. Closer inspection of the spin density plot reveals that the absorption bands in the region 258–525 nm for all complexes have mixed $^1\text{MLCT}$ and $^1\text{ILCT}$ character.

Table 3. Main calculated optical transition for the complex **1** with composition in terms of molecular orbital contribution of the transition, vertical excitation energies, and oscillator strength in dichloromethane

Transition	Composition	E (eV)	Oscillator strength (f)	CI	λ_{theo} (nm)	Assign.	λ_{exp} (nm)
$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO (6%)	2.4896	0.9658	0.179	498	$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	500
	HOMO \rightarrow LUMO (88%)			0.667		$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
	HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 (2%)			0.109		$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
$S_0 \rightarrow S_4$	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (27%)	2.8686	0.0541	-0.369	432	$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	429
	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+2 (54%)			0.520		$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+3 (2%)			0.104		$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}$	
	HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 (6%)			0.171		$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
	HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+2 (6%)			0.176		$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
$S_0 \rightarrow S_{50}$	HOMO-12 \rightarrow LUMO (6%)	4.5478	0.0048	0.185	268	$^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	262
	HOMO-12 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (3%)			0.116		$^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
	HOMO-7 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (2%)			0.109		$^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
	HOMO-7 \rightarrow LUMO+2 (5%)			0.152		$^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	
	HOMO-5 \rightarrow LUMO+4 (77%)			0.619		$^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}/^1\text{LLCT}$	

cally characterized as an admixture of MLCT and ILCT states.

It is clear seen from the NTOs plot that, optical excitations occur from the occupied (hole) transition orbitals to the unoccupied (electron) transition orbitals. In the systems the hole NTOs contributing to the

bands are localized on the Ir center along with π orbitals of ligands ($t_{2g}-\pi$) while the electron NTOs are mainly delocalized over the π^* orbital of the ligand moiety.

It is to be noted that incorporation of 5-arylazo moiety to the 8-hydroxyquinoline moiety results much

$^1\text{MLCT} / ^1\text{ILCT}$			Hole	Electron
505 nm	1	S_2 $w = 0.92$ 2.458 eV (0.001) $t_{2g} - \pi ? \pi^*$		
498 nm	1	S_3 $w = 0.93$ 2.489 eV (0.965) $t_{2g} - \pi ? \pi^*$		
432 nm	1	S_4 $w = 0.66$ 2.869 eV (0.054) $t_{2g} - \pi ? \pi^*$		
268 nm	1	S_{50} $w = 0.26$ 4.548 eV (0.005) $t_{2g} - \pi ? \pi^*$		

Fig. 6. Natural transition orbitals (NTOs) for the complexes **1** illustrating the nature of optically active singlet excited states in the experimental absorption bands 500, 429 and 262 nm. For each state, the respective number of the state, transition energy (eV), and the oscillator strength (in parentheses) are listed. Shown are only occupied (holes) and unoccupied (electrons) NTO pairs that contribute more than 25% to each excited state. All transitions are mixed $^1\text{MLCT}/^1\text{ILCT}$ character : charge is transferred from $t_{2g}-\pi$ hole orbital to the π^* orbital of the ligands.

more intense absorption band in the visible region (430–440) compared to the 8-hydroxyquinoline complexes where 5-arylazo group is absent. The presence of 5-arylazo group enhances the molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) from (11000) to (18000–35000) $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ for all complexes¹⁰.

Emission spectral properties :

The emission spectral behaviour of all were studied at room temperature in dichloromethane solution respectively. The photophysical parameters are listed in Table 4 and Fig. 7 represents the emission spectra of complexes in dichloromethane solution, respectively.

At room temperature in solution state all the complexes are weak emitters having quantum yield in the range $[(1.49-7.37) \times 10^{-3}]$.

Time resolved luminescence spectra proved to be an important tool to understand the decay process and the emissive nature of the complexes. Thus time re-

Fig. 7. Emission spectra of complex 1, 2 and 3 in dichloromethane solution at room temperature.

solved luminescence spectra are recorded for all the complexes. All the complexes display a bi-exponential decay nature and the decay plot is shown in Fig. 8 for complex 1 and for complex 2 and 3 is given in supporting information (Fig. 21 and Fig. 22). The fluorescence life time (τ), radiative (k_r) and nonradiative (k_{nr}) decay rate constant are collected in Table 4.

The photoluminescence property mainly originates from triplet state charge transfer transitions and electron spin density at T_1 state (Fig. 3) reveals the ligand-centered 3IL nature of T_1 state for all complexes. Table 5, Table 10 and Table 11 in supporting information describes the calculated emission energies associated with their oscillator strengths, the main configurations and their assignments as well as the experimental result of complex 1, 2 and 3 respectively. TDDFT study at T_1 state for all complexes corrobo-

Fig. 8. Changes in the time-resolved photoluminescence decay of complex 1 in dichloromethane at room temperature obtained with 500 nm excitation. The emission at 572 nm was monitored for 1.

Complex	λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	λ_{emi} (nm)	Φ ($\times 10^{-3}$)	k_r (s^{-1}) ($\times 10^7$)	k_{nr} (s^{-1}) ($\times 10^9$)	τ_1 (ns)	τ_2 (ns)
1	259 (71206), 429 (23652), 500 (35474)	572	7.37	5.37	7.3	2.84	13.7
2	260 (83048), 437 (17635), 510 (24852)	581	1.49	1.16	7.8	3.31	12.8
3	260 (58233), 440 (12797), 520 (18431)	590	4.13	1.60	3.9	3.04	25.5

rates with the $^3\text{MLCT}$ or $^3\text{ILCT}$ nature for all the transitions.

In order to analyze the nature of emission, we performed an NTO analysis based on the calculated transition density matrices. Fig. 9 in supporting information illustrates the natural transition orbitals (NTOs) for all mononuclear complexes. Based on our TDDFT NTOs analysis at T_1 state all the bands for all the complexes can be characterized as $^3\text{MLCT}$ and $^3\text{ILCT}$ transitions. As illustrated in Fig. 9 (Supporting information) optical excitations occur from the occupied (hole) transition orbitals to the unoccupied (electron) transition orbitals. Both hole and electron NTOs contributing to the bands are mainly ligand localized and somewhat metal localised.

Conclusion

In summary, we have synthesized a family of monomeric phenylpyridine based iridium(III) mixed ligand complexes bearing different arylazo ligands. The complexes are characterized by different spectroscopic techniques, elemental analysis and ^1H NMR spectral analysis as well as IR spectroscopy. The present work investigated the ground- and excited-state geometries, absorption, and phosphorescence properties of three Ir^{III} complexes by DFT and TDDFT methods. We specifically focused on the changes in electronic structure and optical properties of these molecules caused by changing the amine of the azo ligands. We specifically focused on the changes in electronic structure and optical properties of these molecules caused by changing the amine of the azo ligands. Actually we wanted to show how UV and photoluminescence spectra varies with increase in conjugation in the complex of **1** to **3** as we see with increase in conjugation at aryl part, i.e. from benzene to fluorene of the azo there is increase in wavelength shifted from complex **1** to **3** for UV spectroscopy as well as there is a bathochromic shift in the wavelength at photoluminescence spectroscopy as well from complex **1** to **3**. TDDFT investigation gave insights into the optical transitions involved in the excitation process. From our calculation results, we have characterized all of the low-lying electronic states as a mixture of ILCT and MLCT in character. The na-

ture of the transitions was also supported by spin density difference map and natural transition orbital (NTO) analysis. The emission like transition is associated with admixture of strong $^3\text{MLCT}$ and $^3\text{ILCT}$ character for complexes **1**, **2** and **3** as demonstrated by electron spin density analysis. The effect of ancillary ligands on tuning the colour emission is interpreted in terms of the raising/lowering of HOMOs and LUMOs as well as the gaps between them.

Acknowledgements

Financial assistance received from the Science & Engineering Research Board, New Delhi, India is gratefully acknowledged. We are also thankful to Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, India for the data collection on the CCD facility setup (Jadavpur University) under DST-FIST program. We also acknowledge CAS, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University and DST-PURSE program for other facilities. Amit Maity is also thankful to UGC, New Delhi for the research fellowship.

Appendix A. Supporting Information (ESI)

Fig. 9–Fig. 23 and Table 5–Table 11 are provided as electronic supplementary materials in supporting information.

References

- (a) E. C. Constable, M. Neuburger, P. Rosel, G. E. Schneider, J. A. Zampese, C. E. Housecroft, F. Monti, N. Armaroli, R. D. Costa and E. Ortí, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2013, **52**, 885; (b) F. Spaenig, J.-H. Olivier, V. Prusakova, P. Retailleau, R. Ziessel and F. N. Castellano, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **50**, 10859; (c) S. Lamansky, P. Djurovich, D. Murphy, F. Abdel-Razzaq, H.-E. Lee, C. Adachi, P. E. Burrows, S. R. Forrest and M. E. Thompson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 4304.
- (a) W. J. Song, Z. F. Chen, M. K. Brennaman, J. J. Concepcion, A. O. T. Patrocinio, N. Y. Murakami Iha and T. J. Meyer, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2011, **83**, 749; (b) M. Grätzel, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2009, **42**, 1788.
- A. Kumar, S. S. Sun and A. J. Lees, "Photophysics and photochemistry of organometallic rhenium diimine complexes. In : Topics in Organometallic Chemistry", ed. A. J. Lees, Springer, New York, 2010, **29**, 1.
- M. K. Itokazu, A. S. Polo and N. Y. Murakami Iha, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 2003, **160**, 27.
- P. S. Wagenknecht and P. C. Ford, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*,

Maity *et al.* : Synthesis and characterization of heteroleptic iridium(III) complexes incorporating *etc.*

- 2011, **255**, 591.
6. T. Hugel, N. B. Holland, A. Cattani, L. Moroder, M. Seitz and H. E. Gaub, *Science*, 2002, **296**, 1103.
 7. V. Balzani, A. Credi and M. Venturi, *Chem. Phys. Chem.*, 2008, **9**, 202.
 8. M. P. Santoni, G. S. Hanan, B. Hasenknopf, A. Proust, F. Nastasi, S. Serroni and S. Campagna, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 3586.
 9. M. Y. Wong, G. Xie, C. Tourbillon, M. Sandroni, D. B. Cordes, A. M. Z. Slawin, I. D. W. Samuel and E. Zysman-Colman, *Dalton Trans.*, 2015, **44**, 8419.
 10. C. Yi, C.-J. Yang, J. Liu, M. Xu, J.-H. Wang, Q.-Y. Cao and X.-C. Gao, *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, 2007, **360**, 3493.
 11. A. Maity, R. Sarkar and K. K. Rajak, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 7885.
 12. D.-F. Huang, T. J. Chow, C.-Y. Wu, S.-S. Sun, S.-H. Tsai, Y.-S. Wen, S. Polosan and T. Tsuboi, *Journal of the Chinese Chemical Society*, 2008, **55**, 439.
 13. G. Li, Y. Wu, G. Shan, W. Che, D. Zhu, B. Song, L. Yan, Z. Sua and M. R. Bryce, *Chem. Commun.*, 2014, **50**, 6977.
 14. (a) A. D. Becke, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 5648; (b) C. Lee, W. Yang and R. G. Parr, *Phys. Rev. B : Condens. Matter.*, 1988, **37**, 785; (c) B. Miehlich, A. Savin, H. Stoll and H. Preuss, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1989, **157**, 200.
 15. (a) J. S. Binkley, J. A. Pople and W. J. Hehre, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 939; (b) W. J. Stevens, W. J. Basch and M. Krauss, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **81**, 6026; (c) W. J. Stevens, M. Krauss, H. Basch and P. G. Jasien, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1992, **70**, 612; (d) T. R. Cundari and W. J. Stevens, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 5555.
 16. (a) M. S. Gordon, J. S. Binkley, J. A. Pople, W. J. Pietro and W. J. Hehre, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 2797; (b) W. J. Pietro, M. M. Francl, W. J. Hehre, D. J. Defrees, J. A. Pople and J. S. Binkley, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 5039; (c) K. D. Dobbs and W. J. Hehre, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1986, **7**, 359; (d) K. D. Dobbs and W. J. Hehre, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1987, **8**, 861; (e) K. D. Dobbs and W. J. Hehre, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1987, **8**, 880; (f) R. Ditchfield, W. J. Hehre and J. A. Pople, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1971, **54**, 724; (g) W. J. Hehre, R. Ditchfield and J. A. Pople, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1972, **56**, 2257; (h) P. C. Hariharan and J. A. Pople, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **28**, 213; (i) P. C. Hariharan and J. A. Pople, *Mol. Phys.*, 1974, **27**, 209; (j) M. S. Gordon, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1980, **76**, 163.
 17. J. Tomasi, B. Mennucci and R. Cammi, *Chem. Rev.*, 2005, **105**, 2999.
 18. (a) L. Donato, C. E. McCusker, F. N. Castellano and E. Zysman-Colman, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2013, **52**, 8495; (b) A. M. Soliman, D. Fortin, P. D. Harvey and E. Zysman-Colman, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 9382.
 19. X. H. Yang, F. Jaiser, B. Stiller, D. Neher, F. Galbrecht and U. Scherf, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2006, **16**, 2156.
 20. J. Kalinowski, M. Cocchi, D. Virgili, V. Fattori and J. A. G. Williams, *Adv. Mater.*, 2007, **19**, 4000.
 21. S. Lee, K.-H. Kim, D. Limbach, Y.-S. Park and J.-J. Kim, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2013, **23**, 4105.
 22. C. Adachi, M. A. Baldo, M. E. Thompson and S. R. Forrest, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 2001, **90**, 5048.
 23. D. R. Coulson, L. C. Satek and S. O. Grim, in "Inorg. Synth", ed. F. A. Cotton, 2007, 121.
 24. A. Bouillon, J.-C. Lancelot, V. Collot, P. R. Bovy and S. Rault, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 2885.
 25. P. H. Bernardo, T. Sivaraman, K. F. Wan, J. Xu, J. Krishnamoorthy, C. M. Song, L. Tian, J. S. Chin, D. S. Lim, H. Y. Mok, V. C. Yu, J. C. Tong and C. L. Chai, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **53**, 2314.
 26. M. A. Baldo, M. E. Thomson and S. R. Forrest, *Nature*, 2000, **403**, 750.
 27. Y. J. Su, H. L. Huang, C. L. Li, C. H. Chien, Y. T. Tao, P. T. Chou, S. Datta and R. S. Liu, *Adv. Mater.*, 2003, **15**, 884.
 28. C. H. Yang, C. C. Tai and I. W. Sun, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2004, **14**, 947.
 29. E. Holder, B. M. M. Langeveld and U. S. Schubert, *Adv. Mater*, 2005, **17**, 1109.
 30. S. C. Lo, C. P. Shipley, R. N. Bera, R. E. Harding, A. R. Cowley, P. L. Burn and I. D. W. Samuel, *Chem. Mater.*, 2006, **18**, 519.
 31. X. M. Yu, H. S. Kwok, W. Y. Wong and G. J. Zhou, *Chem. Mater.*, 2006, **18**, 5097.
 32. K. Nonoyama, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, **47**, 467.
 33. B. Valuer, "Molecular Fluorescence : Principle and Applications", Wiley-BCH, Weinheim, 2001.
 34. P. Mondal, A. Hens, S. Basak and K. K. Rajak, *Dalton Trans.*, 2013, 1536.
 35. J. V. Houten and R. J. Watts, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 4853.
 36. R. Czerwieniec, A. Kapturkiewicz, R. Anulewicz-Ostrowska and J. Nowacki, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2001, 2756.
 37. H. C. Zhao, B. Mello, B.-L. Fu, H. Chowdhury, D. J. Szalda, M.-K. Tsai, D. C. Grills and J. Rochford, *Organometallics*, 2013, **32**, 1832.

38. A. S. Polo, M. K. Itokazu, K. M. Frin, A. O. T. Patrocinio and N. Y. Murakami Iha, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 1669.
39. M. A. L. Marques and E. K. U. Gross, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 2004, **55**, 427.
40. Y. Wang, Y. Wang, J. Wang, Y. Liu and Y. Yang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 8839.
41. (a) W. Koch and M. C. Holthausen, "A Chemist's Guide to Density Functional Theory", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 2000; (b) P. J. Hay and W. R. Walt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 299.
42. M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Caricato, X. Li, H. P. Hratchian, A. F. Izmaylov, J. Bloino, G. Zheng, J. L. Sonnenberg, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. Brothers, K. N. Kudin, V. N. Staroverov, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, N. Rega, J. M. Millam, M. Klene, J. E. Knox, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, R. L. Martin, K. Morokuma, V. G. Zakrzewski, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, Ö. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, J. Cioslowski and D. J. Fox, Gaussian 09, (Revision A.1), Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford, CT, 2009; E. D. Glendening, A. E. Reed, J. E. Carpenter and F. Weinhold, NBO, version 3.1, University of Madison, 1995.
43. M. L. Deda, A. Grisolia, I. Aiello, A. Crispini, M. Ghedini, S. Belviso, M. Amati and F. Lelj, *Dalton Trans.*, 2004, 2424.